

Effect of graphene nanoparticles and their functionalisation on vitrimer matrix

Q.A. Poutrel^{1,2,*}, Y. Baghdadi^{1,2}, C. Soutis^{1,2}, and M. Gresil^{1,2,*}

¹Aerospace Research Institute, The University of Manchester, Manchester, UK; ²i-Composites Lab, The University of Manchester, Manchester, UK

*Corresponding author (quentin-arthur.poutrel@manchester.ac.uk, matthieu.gresil@manchester.ac.uk)

Tunable mechanical behaviours on a reprocessable thermoset epoxy via graphene enhanced covalent adaptive network

Vitrimer compound and network produced

Graphene (GNP) and its derivatives: graphene oxide (GO) and epoxy functionalised graphene (GPTS-GO)

Evolution of strain at break and tensile stress with graphene loading

Viscosity evolution with temperature. Onset: Arrhenius plot (activation energy)

Motivations

- Vitrimer have been extensively studied since their discovery in 2011⁽¹⁾
- Literature shows limited information about graphene and its functionalisation onto vitrimeric properties (e.g. energy activation)

Results

- Strain at break improved for GO and GPTS-GO compared to GNP due to better bonding with matrix
- Tensile stress and strain at break of GPTS samples are higher due to longer functionalisation chain
- Young's modulus greatly increase for at least one loading of nanoparticles
- At any loading the graphene content decreases the activation energy of vitrimer – the bond exchange needs less energy, making the vitrimer matrix easier to reprocess.
- XRD results shows that GO and GPTS-GO are bond to the matrix
- The glass transition of samples is not (or slightly) affected by particles loading

Methods

Concluding remarks

- Analytical study are required of particles size for further comprehension of mechanical behaviour with different functionalisation
- Adding graphene and/or derivative can increases mechanical properties (e.g. Young modulus) while improving the re-processability of vitrimer network

Additional information

XRD signature for: (a) Raw particles, (b) GNP samples, (c) GO samples and (d) GPTS-GO samples – red dotted line shows maximum of amorphous peak of raw vitrimer, green dotted shows maximum of amorphous peak for graphene samples

Loading	GNP (wt.%)			GO (wt.%)			GPTS-GO (wt.%)			
	0	0.1	0.5	1	0.1	0.5	1	0.1	0.5	1
T _g (tan delta, °C)	40	33	38	36	33	40	36	30	40	37

Glass transition temperature (T_g) of vitrimer samples measured on tan delta curve via dynamical mechanical analysis

⁽¹⁾ Montarnal et al., "Silica-like malleable materials from permanent organic networks", 2012, Science Vol. 334, 6058, pp. 965-968